

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Aralova Iroda Meliqo`zi qizi

NUTQI TO`LIQ RIVOJLANMAGAN BOLALAR BILAN OLIB BORILADIGAN

KORREKTSION - PEDAGOGIK ISH SHAKLLARINI O`RGANISH YO`LLARI

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